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Requirements and architecture definition (update)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAI	Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Confidential Computing
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CoCo	Confidential Container
DNS	Domain Name Service
DNSH	Do No Significant Harm
DRH	Data Rights Holder
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
FDE	Full Disk Encryption
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
NIST	National Institute of Standards & Technology
PBKDF	Password-Based Key Derivation Function
PQC	Post-Quantum Cryptography
SDK	Software Development Kit
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
UX	User eXperience
US	User Stories
VM	Virtual Machine

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is an evaluation and update of the previously published deliverable: “Requirements and architecture definition” [D6.1] for the SIESTA platform, at the end of the first 18 months of the SIESTA project.

Along the path of building the SIESTA platform, a number of issues arose with the platform in its current state of development. The emergence of such problems or adjustments is to be expected in a project requiring the application of strict security policies, a high level of technical expertise and ambitious objectives in an evolving regulatory environment. The project’s rigorous security requirements leave no room for shortcuts in its technical implementation.

Now at its midpoint, a thorough introspection is essential to identify current shortcomings and realign the trajectory toward achieving the project’s final objectives, and establish a sustainable architecture. This will ensure the continued provision and development of SIESTA services beyond the Horizon Europe funding period.

1.2 SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE UPDATE

This evaluation and update will encompass the entire platform, with a comprehensive assessment of all services through the use cases. Feedback collected will highlight gaps and issues, which will then be analysed to determine the necessary modifications to better meet users’ needs. In parallel, both the documentation and the overall User experience (UX) will be reviewed for potential enhancements wherever applicable.

1.3 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The primary objective of this document is to describe an updated version of the SIESTA platform architecture. It is structured as follows:

- In this section (Section 1), the context, objectives and motivations for reviewing and updating the SIESTA platform are presented.
- Section 2 presents a review of the initial service architecture. It also permits a first assessment of the architectural constraints.
- Section 3 covers the use cases’ feedback and the platform gap analysis. It is based on the compilation of the user survey.
- Section 4 details the revised project requirements. It presents the adjustment of initial requirements based on the use cases’ feedback.
- Section 5 is about the updated architecture definition. It includes the detailed modification of the services, documentation, and UX to address the gaps and meet revised requirements.
- Finally in section 6, the plan for ongoing and future modifications to the platform is drawn alongside a roadmap for those to happen, with provisions for additional interactions with the use cases to ensure that the modifications suit them, and that they are properly tested and validated.

2. REVIEW OF THE INITIAL ARCHITECTURE

This section is about the previously proposed architecture, as described in deliverables D6.1 & D7.1. Its goal is to study what was in those proposals and what the concrete implementation work showed us and made us diverge from the initially planned architecture.

2.1 ASSUMPTIONS AND CONSTRAINTS

During the WP6 phase, a significant part of the work involved gathering user requirements. The main outcomes were the following.

2.1.1 Assumptions

Diversity of user profiles

It is assumed that platform users have distinct needs and different levels of access, requiring a granular and flexible authentication and access control system.

Trust in authentication mechanisms

SIESTA uses Keycloak with institutional identity providers (e.g. eduGAIN) to exclude consumer accounts (social networks, unverified ORCID), thereby reducing the risk of identity theft. However, this approach does not yet cover eIDAS 2.0 [\[EIDAS\]](#) requirements, which are expected to be integrated in the medium term, subject to the maturity of European infrastructures [\[EDIW\]](#). This is therefore a transitional situation that guarantees a high level of trust while preparing for a future transition to enhanced authentication through qualified electronic identities.

Secure processing environment

It is assumed that researchers and students are allowed to perform complex processing and analysis in a secure environment without compromising data confidentiality or integrity.

Action traceability

It is assumed that the generation of comprehensive audit logs is technically feasible and will be sufficient to ensure transparency and user accountability.

2.1.2 Constraints

Security and Compliance

Sensitive data must only be accessible to users explicitly authorised by the data right holders, when legally possible. High security standards must be applied to every component. In addition, the platform must comply with applicable regulations (e.g., GDPR), requiring robust mechanisms for encryption, anonymisation, and traceability.

Technical Flexibility

Since each use case relies on different software, processing and analysis solutions, the platform must be adaptable to their needs by adopting proven standards. It must also be able to integrate with existing external systems (e.g., EGI Check-in [\[EGCI\]](#), commercial Cloud providers, ...).

Data Management

Processed data must only be exportable to authorised users, with validation mechanisms such as electronic signatures and auditable logs. All access and actions must be recorded in a tamper-proof and immutable way to enable subsequent verification.

Architectural Adaptability

The architecture must be able to adapt to future changes (e.g., new use cases, regulatory updates) without requiring major redesign. As some services rely on external providers (EGI, software vendors, etc.), continuous monitoring is necessary to anticipate changes on their part (i.e. APIs, access conditions).

2.2 INITIAL ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

This section describes the technological choices made for the initial design of the SIESTA platform, as detailed in [\[D6.1\]](#). These choices form the basis of the platform's architecture. However, some modifications have already been introduced during the WP7 phase in response to technical, organisational or legal constraints. These modifications are presented in section 2.3.

2.2.1 Siesta Service Architecture

The first version of the SIESTA architecture was described in deliverables [D6.1] and [D7.1]. The following figures (Figures 2-4) provide a brief overview of the high-level services.

Figure 1. SIESTA services usages per type.

Figure 2. System landscape.

[Container] SIESTA Common
Friday, 4 July 2023 16:44:17 Central European Summer Time

Figure 3. Common services used by the platform.

[Container] SIESTA Secure Compute
Friday, 4 July 2023 16:44:17 Central European Summer Time

Figure 4. Secure Compute components.

2.2.2 Key Components and Services Overview

The key components and services are summarised below. A more comprehensive description is available in deliverable D6.1. It should also be noted that they have varying levels of technological readiness (TRL), ranging from level 3 (proof of concept) to level 9 (production). The aim is for all services to be at least at level 7 by the end of the SIESTA project, and for it to be ready to move to level 8.

Authentication and User Management

It was initially planned that the web portal relies on EGI Check-in [\[EGCI\]](#), a high-availability authentication service already operated by EGI and widely adopted across the EGI Federation, for providing user and group management.

Access Control and Audit

Access control is delegated to individual service providers. However, auditing is supported by a unified technological solution, combining Google Trillian [\[TRIL\]](#) and BBVA QED [\[QED\]](#). Trillian was selected because it offers several advantages. It combines flexibility (generic logs) and performance (scalability), manageable costs and technology (well-documented open source software), and provides legally robust audit evidence aligned with the project's compliance requirements.

Secure Compute Environments

Two types of secure compute services are provided:

- Remote desktop: delivered through Cendio ThinLinc, with Windows support for specific use cases.
- Interactive analysis: no specific tools are mandated; the platform offers flexible resources that can be adapted to the needs of each use case.

Compute API and Environment

The compute environments are based on OpenStack (SDK/CLI), a widely adopted open-source solution, and on confidential containers (CoCo) for hosting Kubernetes clusters. They can be easily integrated with OpenTofu for deployment automation and Ansible for service configuration. Hashicorp Vault/OpenBao is used for secure secret management, already in production at TRL9 within the EGI Federation.

Secure Storage

The storage solution follows a two-layer approach: raw storage volumes are provided by the cloud middleware, while software encryption is performed within a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) using dedicated secrets.

Data Management

The platform adopts Apache Kafka for data ingestion and OpenSearch/ELK for data stream processing. These software have been chosen for building a secured and robust service: Kafka ensures reliable and scalable data ingestion with TLS encryption and access control (ACLs), while OpenSearch/ELK enables secure centralisation of

logs that are only accessible via defined roles, thus guaranteeing complete traceability and optimal system resilience. Their widespread adoption and dynamic ecosystem make them the de facto standards for critical architectures, benefiting from regular updates and an active community that continually enhances their security and performance. For anonymisation, the ANJANA library is used on structured datasets, while pyCANON is employed to assess anonymity levels. For data egress, any secure transfer method is permitted, provided that users are properly authenticated and authorised.

Development Management

Development is supported through a GitLab instance hosted at IFCA. Dependency management is handled with Sonatype Nexus. Container images are stored in Harbor and continuously scanned for vulnerabilities with Trivy.

2.3 DEPLOYED PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the deployed platform, described in the deliverable D7.1, has some differences from the initial design presented in deliverable D6.1. They mainly consist of complementary components that were introduced to better address project requirements and constraints.

First, regarding the authentication and authorisation infrastructure, it was decided to rely on a self-operated Keycloak [\[KEYC\]](#) service hosted at IFCA. This choice was necessary to ensure timely progress in line with the predefined project schedule and to facilitate the identity provider management. In parallel, the objectives have evolved to align with the recommendations of the EOSC Federation Handbook [\[EFH\]](#), as authentication will ultimately be managed via MyAccessID [\[MAID\]](#).

In terms of the user interface (UI), a dedicated web portal was introduced to simplify the secure deployment of kubernetes services by end-users. This service is based on an Onyxia [\[ONYX\]](#) instance.

To facilitate access to encrypted storage resources, two complementary services were implemented:

A web-based file synchronisation and sharing tool built on the well-known Nextcloud software [\[NEXT\]](#), enabling straightforward upload and sharing of files.

An iRODS-based data lake [\[IROD\]](#), whose modularity allows for the integration of various mechanisms (e.g. anonymisation checks, auditability) required by the identified use cases.

Finally, additional measures were taken to strengthen the platform's security. In particular, the Wazuh solution [\[WAZU\]](#) was deployed to enable proactive threat detection.

Overall, these changes represent incremental adjustments rather than major architectural shifts and are detailed in Figure 5. The final set of modifications to the initial architecture will be guided by feedback from the use cases, as described in the following section.

Figure 5. SIESTA general architecture.

3. USE CASE FEEDBACK

3.1 METHODOLOGY

To gather detailed feedback from the use cases, an online survey [SVEY] was developed with contributions from both platform operators and representatives of the use cases. Its aim was to provide a comprehensive form relevant to the different categories of project stakeholders. The questionnaire, detailed in Annex 1, is organized based on user categories, with content tailored and shown accordingly across the following four sections:

General Feedback – establishing the user's role and collecting high-level impressions about the overall SIESTA platform experience.

- Identifies the role of the respondent: Data Rights Holder, Data User, Platform Operator.
- Gathers subjective satisfaction ratings and insights on strengths and weaknesses.
- Helps triangulate functional feedback with perceived usefulness and pain points across roles.

Data Rights Holder – assessing whether the platform supports secure, compliant, and user-friendly data contribution and management workflows.

- Validates data onboarding processes (depositing, curation, anonymization).
- Evaluates controls for access delegation, audit logging, and time-restricted sharing.
- Reviews data integration, governance, and privacy-preserving synthetic data capabilities.
- Ensures legal compliance (GDPR, statistical confidentiality) and administrative control (e.g., Intermediate Administrative Data Center functionality).

Data User – verifying usability, completeness, and performance of the research-oriented features and datasets available in the platform.

- Validates environment setup (custom libraries, ...).
- Reviews user journey from authentication to script execution and results export.
- Assesses dataset availability, metadata richness, anonymization quality, and linkage tools.
- Explores advanced user needs like model training, automated search, and privacy-preserving analysis.

Siesta Platform Operator – evaluating operational robustness, maintainability, security, and user support across core infrastructure services.

- Monitors platform services experience: containers, VMs, storage, DNS, AAI, analytics, data lakes, image registries, etc.
- Captures performance and reliability perceptions of each service.

- Explores configurability (permissions, access control), vulnerability management, and compliance.
- Reviews administrative capabilities for monitoring, auditing, support, and incident response.

This conditional display ensured that respondents only answered questions relevant to their role, enhancing both the quality and the relevance of the collected feedback.

Although the questionnaire contains numerous questions, responding to most of them was optional. Each section concludes with a free-text field to capture points that may not have been addressed by the questions. The objective was to collect the largest possible number of responses. Where answers were incomplete or unclear, the work conducted within WP19 will allow us to refine them.

3.2 KEY FINDINGS

The survey collected approximately more than 40 answers and covers 4 out of 5 use cases. This document includes preliminary requirements of Predictia's, as their late onboarding in the project hampered their availability to answer the questionnaire properly. Although the level of platform usage varies from one use case to another, all comments were considered with equal weight, with the goal of delivering a platform usable by all use cases at the end of WP9. The survey highlighted both what is working well and what needs improvement.

The platform, as currently deployed, is already working correctly for at least part of the use cases. The reported feedback was that, despite still being in development, the platform was usable and permitted to generate non-sensitive synthetic data that is reusable & suitable for research. Regarding storage, some performance issues have been reported. They are currently being investigated by the SIESTA platform's operators in order to identify the causes and provide a solution. However, no availability issues have been reported so far, confirming the overall stability of the services.

The platform is still not completely usable as-is for all envisioned use cases. Below, the main areas for improvement identified through this survey are summarized:

- Not all services are used by the current use cases' users.
- Difficulty in finding relevant services
- Difficulty in finding relevant people to help
- Difficulty in finding relevant (meta-)data
- Unclear answers to regulation & legal questions
- Trust issues (this is strongly related to the previous point).
- Missing or incomplete platform documentation
- Services lack user-friendliness and/or require excessive technical knowledge.
- Services availability status is not sufficiently displayed

3.3 IDENTIFIED GAPS AND IMPROVEMENT AREAS

Based on the constructive criticisms and comments provided by the use cases through the survey, the preliminary discussions with the latest use case – which joined the project at a later stage and was unable to complete the questionnaire due to time

constraints – and the recommendations outlined in the mid-term review report, a comprehensive gap analysis was carried out. This analysis aims to ensure that the SIESTA platform evolves in alignment with user needs, security best practices, and regulatory requirements. The results of the gap analysis are as follows:

Documentation & Specifications

- Clarification and completion of persona/role definitions with permissions, platform workflows, and security incident procedures are required to ensure operational transparency and user trust.
- Active technological monitoring must be maintained to reinforce and justify technical solution choices in a highly dynamic technological environment.
- Post-quantum cryptography risks were identified as a critical gap in the networking section (D6.1, section 5.1.7). An assessment of potential vulnerabilities and a migration plan toward NIST-approved post-quantum algorithms [\[NPQC\]](#) will be included in D9.1.
- Security incident procedures: Draft and publish comprehensive security procedures for the SIESTA platform.

Service and Data Catalogues

- Service catalogue: Clear contact points for issue reporting and support must be documented to improve user experience and accountability.
- Data & metadata catalogue: This new service is required to ensure full compliance with FAIR principles, including detailed metadata schemas and data access procedures.

Legal and Environmental Compliance

- Legal framework/paperwork/workflows: Streamline and document legal processes (e.g., data sharing agreements, GDPR compliance) to ensure clarity and consistency for all stakeholders.
- "Do No Significant Harm" [\[DNSH\]](#) principle: The environmental impact of the cloud-based infrastructure was flagged as insufficiently addressed. A dedicated mitigation plan will be developed to assess risks (e.g., energy consumption, carbon emissions) and implement sustainable practices.

Trust and Support Mechanisms

- Trust must be earned by the platform: Operations must be transparent, particularly regarding security and technological choices, to strengthen user confidence.
- Service status availability should be easy to check
- Issue reporting & support contacts: Establish clear and accessible channels for users to report issues and receive timely support.

- Platform operators acting on behalf of Data Rights Holders: Draft, implement, and publish procedures enabling operators to act as authorized delegates of Data Rights Holders.

3.4 USE CASE SUMMARY

Some use cases adopted the platform early and/or extensively, whereas some others did not. Among the users who have not yet used the platform, two main explanations were given:

- For some, they simply have not had the opportunity to use the platform yet, but they see no limiting issues preventing them from doing so in the near future.
- For others, the situation is more complex: the sensitivity of the data they work with does not allow them to transfer it to the platform due to legal constraints.

In addition, the close collaboration with the medical imaging use case (WP15) has made us aware of the diversity of users who interact with the platform, and of the fact that not everyone will be able to configure complex cloud services. Further work is needed in this area to make the platform easier for end users to understand and operate. Significant frontend work (UI/UX) will be required to achieve this.

Another important point that emerged is that the platform should initially focus on a limited set of services, but with a strong emphasis on ease of use so that the use cases can readily integrate them into their workflows. This core platform will then be progressively enriched through several development cycles, adding complementary features that will expand the range of available services.

4. MODIFICATION OF THE REQUIREMENTS DEFINITION

Analysis of the results of the user survey presented in the previous chapter allows us to update the requirements of the use cases in relation to the SIESTA platform. In this section, the new functional and non-functional requirements are detailed, as well as those that have become obsolete.

4.1 NEW FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Functional requirements define functions or specific behaviours that the SIESTA platform must perform to meet the user needs. The analysis of the user feedback enabled us to identify two crucial missing tools:

- A dataset catalogue
- A service catalogue

For each of these tools, users have specified detailed functional requirements.

4.1.1 Dataset Catalogue

The dataset catalogue provides access to a range of information about datasets hosted on the SIESTA platform, including the data access policy. Due to the sensitive nature of the data, direct access is restricted. The catalogue presents the datasets and offers a variety of search and browsing functions. The catalogue plays a key role regarding the FAIR principles as it enables:

- Findability: it facilitates data discovery
- Accessibility: it describes data access policy
- Interoperability: structured metadata ensures compatibility between systems (for example, it permits to be harvested from other dataset catalogues at EOSC level),
- Reusability: information about the data licences and lifespans.

The dataset catalogue relies on metadata that complies with the Dublin Core standard [\[DUBC\]](#). The functional requirements are classified in the five categories below.

Dataset discovery and management

- Advanced dataset search with full-text, faceted filters, and saved searches.
- Dataset registration with mandatory metadata (title, owner, steward, schema, sensitivity, licence, legal basis).
- Dataset and field-level classification into sensitivity categories with customizable taxonomies.
- Privacy-preserving dataset views (masking, tokenization, anonymization).

Metadata and schema management

- Management of schemas and metadata with support for evolution, validation, and change logs.
- Dataset and schema versioning with immutable snapshots for audit purposes.
- Tracking lineage and provenance across ingestion, transformation, and derived datasets.
- Compatibility declarations to ensure datasets are only processed in approved services.
- A curation system needs to be available to ensure that the metadata does not include sensitive information, as defined in the D5.1 deliverable.

Data governance and legal compliance

- Capturing and enforcing lawful bases and consent scopes for dataset usage.
- Policy definition and linking policies to access and usage enforcement.
- User-driven access requests, approvals, and revocations with full auditability.
- Mechanisms to attach, accept, and version Data Use Agreements.
- Enforcement of jurisdictional restrictions and residency requirements.

Data quality and security

- Generation of dataset quality metrics and notifications for threshold breaches.
- Automated detection of personal and sensitive data fields with data steward confirmation.
- Secure ingestion of data with schema validation, quality checks, and quarantining.
- Retention management and deletion/anonymization according to policies.
- Controlled exports of datasets.

Auditing and incident management

- Tamper-evident audit logs and compliance reporting for dataset usage.
- Mechanisms to flag datasets affected by incidents or breaches and notify consumers.

4.1.2 Service Catalogue

The service catalogue is an organized collection of all the services offered by the SIESTA platform, accompanied by detailed information. This information typically includes:

- The name of the service
- A description of the service
- Conditions of access and use
- Legal entity responsible for the service
- The level of service (TRL)
- Point of contact
- Support address
- Reference to the documentation

The following functional requirements have been defined through the survey and will serve as the foundation for shaping the service catalogue.

Service Overview

- Provide a static directory of available services with their descriptions and an overview of their main features.
- Provide additional metadata such as owner, service level, and support contacts.
- Document interfaces, endpoints, and authentication requirements.
- Document maximum allowed data sensitivity per service.

Compliance, security, and dependencies

- Provide details on residency guarantees and supported processing regions for each service (access policy).
- Provide security and compliance information such as certifications and encryption standards.
- Provide an overview of service dependencies and available integrations.

Documentation and User Support

- Support linking to user guides, tutorials, and onboarding material.
- Provide up-to-date information on service operational status.
- Support a feedback mechanism for service improvements and issue reporting.
- Enable responsible disclosure for security-related incidents, allowing operators to process them to a successful ending.

4.2 NEW NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

In addition to functional requirements, non-functional requirements were also collected through the survey. These requirements help define how the platform should operate and contribute to building trust among stakeholders.

Documentation and Compliance

- Provide centralized documentation and procedures related to legal aspects, covering the responsibilities of Data Rights Holders (DRH) and resource provider sites for handling sensitive data.
- Document end-to-end processes for each persona/role.
- Consideration of environmental impacts and publication of related policies
- Include regulatory and legal framework, with specific subsections for each platform role.
- Provide an easily-accessible "service weather report" site, redundantly hosted.

Authentication and Authorization (AAI Integration)

- All services hosted by the SIESTA project and published in the Service Catalogue must be integrated with the central AAI system.

Security and Trust

- Establish a proper legal framework and workflows to ensure trust between the data rights holders and the platform operators.
- Conduct external security audits.
- Apply security hardening measures and define security policies.
- Provide mechanisms for handling security-related issues [\[REDI\]](#).
- Implement a public issue management solution [\[ISSU\]](#).

Post-quantum threat analysis

Post-quantum cryptography (PQC) has been gaining relevance in recent years due to advances in quantum computer research. These advances make it essential to assess the potential impact of quantum threats on existing security mechanisms. As stated by NIST, if large-scale quantum computers are ever built, they would be able to break many of the public-key cryptosystems currently in use [NIST]. Therefore, the research community is currently evaluating and investigating quantum-resistant public-key cryptographic algorithms that can mitigate these risks, in order to standardize them. Therefore, we have conducted an assessment and preliminary study of post-quantum threats from a theoretical perspective and reviewed the available technologies in that regard concerning data at rest, data in transit, and SSH-based communications within the SIESTA ecosystem.

Regarding data at rest, the foundations on which the SIESTA low-level secure storage services are built, –based on LUKS full disk encryption (FDE) technology with argon2id-based PBKDF [\[ARG2\]](#)– are not directly threatened by quantum attacks, and their safety margin remains sufficient in known PQC threat models.

For data in transit (i.e. the network transfers based on TLS) the configuration must be reviewed to ensure the use of PQC-resistant algorithms and hybrid key exchange protocols as defined in emerging standards. The study of the following documents: [\[PQTL\]](#) and [\[PQCR\]](#), alongside the security hardening work from WP12 will ensure the subject is properly handled.

For SSH-based communications, there are already PQC-resistant algorithms and hybrid key exchange mechanisms available, such as sntrup761x25519-sha512 [\[SSHNTRU\]](#) (based on Streamlined NTRU Prime sntrup761 and X25519 with SHA-512). The use of this kind of protocols will be analyzed and regular auditing will be performed.

Lastly, for the data in use, SIESTA leverages TEE memory encryption, where the cryptographic algorithms used are implemented directly in silicon and are therefore fixed and not configurable by software. The hardware transparently encrypts and decrypts memory regions using predefined symmetric algorithms (typically AES-XTS or AES-GCM), with keys that are generated and managed internally by the processor. These keys never leave the hardware boundary and are derived from a hardware root of trust or secure enclave, making them inaccessible to the operating system or any external process. While this design ensures strong protection against most software- and hypervisor-level attacks, it also means that post-quantum or any other custom encryption methods cannot be applied to the in-memory data of a TEE.

Environmental sustainability

As the project not only has partners in common with the GreenDIGIT [GRED] project (CSIC, CNRS), but also stakeholders who are sensitive to this issue, environmental sustainability is a key criterion among the non-functional requirements. Minimising and controlling environmental impact must be ensured in the implementation of the SIESTA infrastructure. To this end, several actions must be implemented in parallel with the other project's requirements:

- Measurement and optimisation: measuring the energy consumption of components and implementing corrective action in the event of deviations; precise sizing of resources to avoid over-provisioning. SIESTA will produce, during the second half of the project, documentation on how to measure the energy consumption of the platform, aligned with the GreenDIGIT methodologies.
- User awareness: Transparent information on the energy impact of tools (e.g. carbon cost of queries or processing) to encourage responsible use. To this aim SIESTA will leverage wattnet [WATN] a tool developed by CSIC in the context of the GreenDIGIT project that allows to obtain real-time, historical, and forecasted data on the carbon and water impact of electricity consumption across Europe.
- Choice of equipment suppliers: favour certified equipment (e.g. Energy Star, EPEAT, etc.) and eco-efficient hardware and software architectures.
- Software monitoring and frugality: Gradual replacement of energy-intensive components with more efficient alternatives (e.g. switch to lightweight versions of software, optimisation of pipelines).
- Green computing policy: formalisation of an internal charter including monitoring indicators (e.g. data center PUE, resource utilisation rate) and continuous improvement objectives, aligned with GreenDIGIT deliverables in terms of sustainable infrastructure.

4.3 OBSOLETE REQUIREMENTS

The evolution of the SIESTA platform, based on the use case feedback, will include new tools, such as the dataset catalogue and the service catalogue. Unlike other projects where certain features become obsolete, none of the requirements defined in WP6 have been removed. All initial requirements remain fully relevant and aligned with the platform's current needs.

5. UPDATED ARCHITECTURE DEFINITION

This section presents the updated status of the SIESTA platform architecture, building on the initial design described in D6.1 and the subsequent refinements introduced during WP7.

5.1 OVERALL ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

While the core design decisions on the architecture remain valid, there were some services and modules that were identified to be desirable in the platform and thus, following the changes done during the WP7 and the feedback gathered during WP8 these new services are projected to be part of the platform. These additions to the architecture are reflected in the updated figures shown below. These services and modules are now part of the reference architecture and will be progressively implemented and validated within WP9 with some of them like the issue tracking system (helpdesk) being already in use successfully by the users of the platform. The details of these services can be found in sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2.

Figure 6. System landscape (updated).

[Container] SIESTA Common
Tuesday 23 September 2025 at 16:22 Central European Summer Time

Figure 7. Common services (updated).

[Container] SIESTA Secure Compute
Tuesday 23 September 2025 at 10:29 Central European Summer Time

Figure 8. Secure Compute components (updated).

5.2 DEPRECATED SERVICES AND MODULES

Some components initially deployed within the SIESTA architecture were identified as underused or redundant in light of the new services introduced. Maintaining them not only ties up technical and human resources that could be better used elsewhere, but also exposes the project to security and image risks due to a lack of active updates and support. These components will therefore be discontinued in order to optimize resource allocation and focus efforts on priority services.

The component, whose removal is most noticeable, is the Secure Data Lake - it has proved to be unnecessary for the project's use cases. Decommissioning this service will free up development and maintenance resources, allowing the platform's operators to focus on deploying new services that were not initially planned but are now crucial to the success of the SIESTA project.

5.3 NEW SERVICES AND MODULES

As part of the implementation of the platform services (WP7), several components have been added or modified compared to the initial architecture defined in WP6, in order to meet the identified functional and non-functional requirements. The list of these new components is supplemented by those identified in WP8. The new architecture will incorporate all these developments, which will enhance security, interoperability and user experience, while aligning the platform with FAIR principles and use case feedback.

5.3.1 Services added during WP7

Discussions between SIESTA platform administrators and use cases during WP7 identified several services to be added.

Keycloak-based identity provider

EGI Check-in [EGCI] was selected at the launch of the SIESTA project to manage access to infrastructure, due to its native integration with the EGI and EOSC ecosystem to which the infrastructure sites were already federated, and the dynamism of developments supported by H2020 EGI-ACE and EOSC-Future funding. However, three limitations prompted a reassessment of its use across all SIESTA services:

- Identity certification: The inability to certify social identity providers (Google, LinkedIn), a requirement of data rights holders to ensure access traceability.
- Technical blockage: The simultaneous deployment of the new version of EGI Check-in blocked the integration of services, impacting the project schedule.
- Strategic alignment: The selection of MyAccessID by the European Commission EOSC EU Node in 2024 made it necessary to adapt to ensure future compatibility.

EGI Check-in is used for authentication and authorization at the infrastructure level, as our cloud infrastructures (OpenStack sites at IISAS, IFCA, and CNRS) are already integrated with this service.

Therefore, in order to mitigate the issues identified above, Keycloak [\[KEYC\]](#) was chosen to enable granular access control at the EOSC-SIESTA platform level (including the dashboard, container registry, confidential containers, and other components). We rely on EOSC-SIESTA Keycloak to provide greater flexibility, fine-grained role-based access control (RBAC), and to ensure that the EOSC-SIESTA platform remains independent from external authentication services.

This solution is based on widely deployed, robust software that uses interoperable standards with the AAI solution selected by the European Commission in its call for tenders. It is operated by the SIESTA platform administrators and hosted at IFCA.

Intrusion detection system (Wazuh)

Wazuh [\[WAZU\]](#) has been deployed to provide real-time monitoring and auditing of security events.

Web interface for application management (Onyxia)

An instance of Onyxia [\[ONYX\]](#) has been deployed to provide a unified interface allowing users to:

- Configure, deploy and monitor applications securely.
- Benefit from an integrated environment for launching containerised or cloud-based applications.

This interface simplifies access to resources while ensuring compliance with the platform's security policies.

5.3.2 Additional services identified during WP8

Output of works completed during WP8 allows us to add a few services to the previous list, based on an analysis of the survey responses and comments from the SIESTA platform administrators.

Issue tracking system

A GitLab code repository has been integrated in the platform during WP7. Due to its ease of use and intuitive interface, it was proposed during WP8 to base ticket management on this GitLab instance. Moreover, with the creation of issue templates, and their use for issue reporting, tracking and solving, the choice of GitLab is made straightforward and this has become the standard workflow for development since the advent of the agile principles in the DevOps culture. A SIESTA on-premise hosted GitLab instance was preferred over externally managed solutions (such as github) because we will have more control over its management and evolution, which may not stay aligned with the SIESTA platform goals for those private sector owned companies.

Data set catalogue

This service enables discovery, classification and management of metadata in accordance with FAIR principles and the Dublin Core [\[DUBC\]](#) standard. It includes advanced search features, data set versioning and policy-based access control (see section [4.1.1](#)).

A few Open Source software programmes are available to meet users' needs, like:

- Datahub [[DHUB](#)] - an open-source metadata management solution that enables data to be catalogued, discovered and managed, while automating its traceability.
- OpenMetadata [[OPMD](#)] - an open-source data governance and discovery solution that centralises metadata, automates its collection, and offers advanced features to improve trust.
- DSPACE [[DSPA](#)] - an open-source institutional repository management solution enabling organisations to store, preserve, index, and disseminate digital content.

The choice of these software packages is based on quality criteria (development vitality, number of users, etc.) and suitability for the use case requirements. Choosing between these software programmes is one of the first tasks to be completed in WP9.

Service catalogue

This service centralises information on available services (name, description, access conditions, technological maturity level, contacts). It facilitates service discoverability and usability. In particular, it will include the documentation for all SIESTA platform services.

Two types of tools can be used:

1. Highly integrated tools, such as Backstage [[BACS](#)]
2. Lighter tools, based on Jekyll [[JEKY](#)], for example.

Jekyll has many advantages, such as:

- Ease of configuration and integration into the environment with Gitlab.
- Extensibility (ability to use plugins, integration of operational status badges, etc.).
- Easy adoption: Markdown and Git are already widely used in the scientific community, facilitating collaborative contributions.

Given the advantages of Jekyll, the tool will initially be tested to create the service catalogue. It should be noted that this same tool can be used for dynamic display of service status.

Legal management module for data processing and control

This module centralises and provides access to legal agreements signed between entities providing the SIESTA platform (e.g. IFCA, CNRS, IISAS) and data rights holders (DRH). It does not replace the signing processes (which remain the responsibility of the legal entities), but provides a dedicated space for publishing and consulting:

- GDPR-compliant data processing agreements (DPAs), specifying the roles (data controller/processor) and responsibilities of each party.

- Data transfer agreements, including standard contractual clauses for processors.
- Delegation agreements for sensitive operations (access, processing, export).

Documents may be made available either via the services catalogue or in any places recommended by the legal framework, with a public version (anonymised if necessary) and a restricted version for authorised stakeholders.

5.4 UPDATED GENERAL ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

The platform architecture and associated diagrams have been updated to incorporate internal feedback (from the use case survey and initial WP19 meetings) and external recommendations (particularly those from the mid-term evaluation report). This section presents the updated general architecture schema, reflecting the changes and improvements proposed throughout this document, in order to align the design with the identified operational needs and technical requirements.

Figure 9. Updated SIESTA general architecture.

6. IMPLEMENTATION AND INTEGRATION ROADMAP

6.1 DEPLOYMENT PLAN

Work on the necessary enhancements has already begun (or will commence immediately), with progress monitored in close coordination with WP19. Bi-weekly meetings are held for each use case, supplemented by direct communication with the relevant stakeholders. The primary objectives are :

- Set up and test the new services identified in this work package and bring them to the production level
- Resolve the most critical issues raised by the use cases
- Assess the overall architecture and draft a roadmap to fix the remaining minor issues

The implementation of concrete solutions will be distributed across the active technical work packages according to their respective areas of responsibility:

- WP9: implementation and deployment of platform services.
- WP11: development of solutions for data encryption and transfer.
- WP12: security hardening (infrastructure and services).

6.2 FOLLOW-UP WITH THE USE CASES

The priority of Work Package 19 is to follow up on and ensure adoption of the outcomes from the use cases. Launched in July 2025, it is scheduled to run until the end of the project. Building on the foundations established by work-packages WP14 to WP18, WP19 extends and refines this earlier work.

Its main role is to facilitate interaction across teams, helping to identify common challenges that require discussion in use case sessions or global meetings. By using issue tracking, WP19 supports parallel progress on multiple tasks across different resource provider sites.

All platform improvements are documented in an [\[ISSU\]](#) project repository through the GitLab tracking system provided by SIESTA. An initial set of issues has already been compiled based on feedback from the project questionnaire. Some of these will need to be refined or broken down into smaller, more manageable tasks to address their complexity effectively.

The first WP19 meetings, with strong participation from the WP9 team, indicated a shared agreement among participants that while the backend architecture is solid and well-developed, considerable efforts are still required to implement and/or enhance the user interface and improve the overall user experience. It is expected that the close cooperation between WP9 and WP19 will continue, with the WP9 team presenting new developments and updates of the platform services and receiving feedback directly from use cases through joint WP9–WP19 meetings.

6.3 TESTING AND VALIDATION ACTIVITIES

The testing and validation will be handled primarily by the issue creator, and progress will be discussed within the WP19 meetings to ensure no important issue is forgotten. During the WP9 timeframe, use cases encountering the same issue (or similar enough) will also help handle the testing breadth and diversity of applicability for the fixes being provided.

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7. CONCLUSION

The SIESTA platform in its current state has a solid foundation, especially given the use of secure storage and confidential computing well integrated in the backend services. It clearly meets the initial requirements defined in deliverable D6.1, while having undergone iterative adjustments to respond to initial feedback from use cases and platform administrators during WP7. The decision to base the architecture on interoperable components from the outset made it possible to make adjustments without compromising the architecture itself.

In order for the platform to become an accessible and useful tool for all stakeholders –whether they are technical experts or business users– significant efforts still need to be made, particularly in the following areas:

- User experience: the development of an integrated frontend is a priority in order to simplify access to services and make them intuitive, regardless of users' technical level and profile.
- Training and support: not all use cases will have qualified human resources to manage critical security issues past the end-date of the SIESTA project, such as handling secrets or legal compliance. Enhanced support and practical guides will be necessary to ensure secure and effective use.

Improvement work has already begun, and progress is visible thanks to the ticket management system and is being closely monitored by WP19. The role of site administrators has also been strengthened, as they will not only have to provide resources, but also get involved in liaising with high-level users of use cases:

- By working to establish a framework that ensures legal compliance.
- By facilitating the integration of services in heterogeneous environments, while maintaining a high level of data protection.

In conclusion, the SIESTA platform has now a solid technical and organisational foundation, but its long-term success will depend on its ability to combine security and simplicity – challenges that the SIESTA team will face, relying on a collaborative and iterative approach.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX I - USE CASE SURVEY

SIESTA WP8 User Survey

The main objective of Work Package 8 (WP8) is to align the SIESTA platform architecture with real user needs by integrating structured feedback collected from current users. This process is crucial in guiding development teams toward a final production-ready version of the platform that delivers both functional completeness and user satisfaction.

To support this effort, the following questionnaire has been prepared. It is structured around the original User Stories that informed the platform design and development. For each user, a set of validation questions is provided to assess whether the expected functionality is fully covered, usable, and reliable in the running system.

We kindly ask each user to complete the questionnaire thoroughly. Your responses will help identify strengths, expose any gaps or limitations, and provide valuable insight for further improvements. This collaborative review is key to ensuring the SIESTA platform fulfils its mission of enabling secure, efficient, and user-centred data-driven research.

There are 164 questions in this survey.

Section 1. General Feedback

What is your role when using the platform? *

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

1. Data Rights Holder
2. Data User (Scientist)
3. SIESTA Platform Operator (Admin)

Did you use the SIESTA platform? *

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

How is your overall satisfaction with the platform? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '2 [A2A0]' (Did you use the SIESTA platform?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

1. Very Satisfied
2. Satisfied
3. Neutral
4. Dissatisfied
5. Very Dissatisfied
6. No opinion

What are the top 3 most useful features for you?

What are the top 3 features you believe are missing or need improvement?

Section 2. Data Rights Holder

For all questions in this group (except the last one), you can simply answer with "Yes" ("Y") or "No" ("N"). However, the short text field permits you also to elaborate on your answer. Please feel free to use it for any additional comments or explanations.

Some questions may not apply to you, or you may not be able to answer them at this time. Please feel free to skip any such questions. If you find that you cannot answer most of the survey, please use the final section to explain why.

1. Were you able to deposit your datasets without repeatedly signing paperwork?

Please write your answer here:

2. Was the process of dataset preparation and curation aligned with the recommended standards?

Please write your answer here:

3. Was the feedback provided by the platform clear and actionable for corrections?

Please write your answer here:

4. Did the platform notify you when your dataset was successfully validated and deposited?

Please write your answer here:

5. Did the storage environment provide clear mechanisms for ensuring data security and sensitivity handling?

Please write your answer here:

6. Could you verify the level of anonymity of uploaded data using built-in tools?

Please write your answer here:

7. Were additional anonymization techniques available and easy to apply when needed?

Please write your answer here:

8. Was the overall upload process efficient and user-friendly?

Please write your answer here:

9. Were you provided with a clear and complete list of potential data reusers?

Please write your answer here:

10. Could you define access rights for each user or group individually?

Please write your answer here:

11. Could you organize or manage access groups easily?

Please write your answer here:

12. Was it possible to limit data access to a specific timeframe?

Please write your answer here:

13. Did the platform support secure interdepartmental data sharing?

Please write your answer here:

14. Was data encryption enforced during transmission between users or departments?

Please write your answer here:

15. Were access controls and user permissions reliable?

Please write your answer here:

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16. Could you track or audit how shared data was accessed and used?

Please write your answer here:

17. Did the platform reduce dependency on manual or external sharing methods?

Please write your answer here:

18. Were you able to configure automated workflows for integrating data from different sources?

Please write your answer here:

19. Did the automated data ingestion process reduce manual errors?

Please write your answer here:

20. Was the data integration logic transparent and modifiable as needed?

Please write your answer here:

21. Were success/failure logs or data integration reports available for review?

Please write your answer here:

22. Did data ingestion automation improve the speed and reliability of integration activities?

Please write your answer here:

23. Were logs of sharing actions detailed, accurate, and up to date?

Please write your answer here:

24. Could you generate reports based on sharing activity (by user, time period, dataset, etc.)?

Please write your answer here:

25. Did the audit capability help enforce internal data governance policies?

Please write your answer here:

26. Could you verify that re-identification of anonymized data was not possible?

Please write your answer here:

27. Was the anonymized data still usable for research and policy-making purposes?

Please write your answer here:

28. Did the platform allow testing of privacy vs. utility trade-offs?

Please write your answer here:

29. Were regulatory and ethical standards reflected in the anonymization processes?

Please write your answer here:

30. Were you able to generate synthetic data using the platform?

Please write your answer here:

31. Did the synthetic data closely reflect the structure and behavior of real data?

Please write your answer here:

32. Could you confirm that synthetic data did not expose actual

identities?

Please write your answer here:

33. Was the generated data suitable for research or policy applications?

Please write your answer here:

34. Were you able to control generation parameters to fine-tune the synthetic datasets?

Please write your answer here:

35. Did the platform allow customization of anonymization and synthetic data settings?

Please write your answer here:

36. Could users adjust privacy levels or parameters to suit specific needs?

Please write your answer here:

37. Was statistical quality preserved across different configurations?

Please write your answer here:

38. Were customization features easy to understand and apply?

Please write your answer here:

39. Did the platform enforce safeguards against generating data with re-identification risks?

Please write your answer here:

40. Did the platform offer an Intermediate Administrative Data Center for handling data requests?

Please write your answer here:

41. Could the center serve both public and private sector needs efficiently?

Please write your answer here:

42. Were data outputs customizable per user request?

Please write your answer here:

43. Was legal compliance (e.g., GDPR, statistical confidentiality) ensured during the data provisioning process?

Please write your answer here:

44. Did the platform balance privacy with flexibility in how data was served?

Please write your answer here:

45. Additional comments

Please write your answer here:

Section 3. Data User (Scientist)

For all questions in this group (except the last one), you can simply answer with "Yes" ("Y") or "No" ("N"). However, the short text field permits you also to elaborate on your answer. Please feel free to use it for any additional comments or explanations.

Some questions may not apply to you, or you may not be able to answer them at this time. Please feel free to skip any such questions. If you find that you cannot answer most of the survey, please use the final section to explain why.

1. Were you able to sign in and access the platform without excessive paperwork or administrative delays?

Please write your answer here:

2. Was the regulatory disclaimer (e.g., on not identifying or exporting personal data) clear and acceptable?

Please write your answer here:

3. Could you import or request dedicated software applications for your work?

Please write your answer here:

4. Were you able to test your scripts on anonymous data as intended?

Please write your answer here:

5. Is the overall performance of the platform satisfactory?

Please write your answer here:

6. Were you able to iterate on your analysis steps efficiently (e.g., rerun your scripts)?

Please write your answer here:

7. Could you export anonymous results (e.g., tables or figures) without technical or policy obstacles?

Please write your answer here:

8. Did the platform allow access to verified software repositories (e.g., PyPI)?

Please write your answer here:

9. Were you able to successfully install all necessary libraries and dependencies?

Please write your answer here:

10. If additional software sources were needed, was the process of adding them straightforward?

Please write your answer here:

11. Did the system reliably check installed software for known vulnerabilities?

Please write your answer here:

12. Were there any limitations or security-related constraints that impacted your setup?

Please write your answer here:

13. Was the list of available datasets accessible and easy to browse?

Please write your answer here:

14. Were the permissions for each dataset clearly explained before access?

Please write your answer here:

15. Did the platform describe allowed actions on each dataset explicitly?

Please write your answer here:

16. Was it clear which datasets contained sensitive or anonymized information?

Please write your answer here:

17. Could you view metadata for datasets before requesting access?

Please write your answer here:

18. Did the metadata provide enough information to assess dataset relevance?

Please write your answer here:

19. Was sensitive or protected metadata appropriately hidden or generalized?

Please write your answer here:

20. Was the request process for accessing specific datasets well-structured and justified?

Please write your answer here:

21. Did the platform provide feedback or approval status on your dataset requests?

Please write your answer here:

22. Were you able to create your own software environment within the platform?

Please write your answer here:

23. Were you able to set up a fully functional research environment (software, storage, ...) within the platform?

Please write your answer here:

24. Did the platform offer a research-oriented user interface such as Jupyter Notebook or RStudio?

Please write your answer here:

25. Could you use programming languages like Python, R, or C++ to build custom models?

Please write your answer here:

26. Was access to datasets (e.g., synthetic population, mixing matrices, OD matrices, vector prevalence) reliable and performant?

Please write your answer here:

27. Was the environment stable and responsive while building and running models?

Please write your answer here:

28. Could you generate or edit training code within the platform?

Please write your answer here:

29. Did the system restrict access only to anonymized datasets for model training?

Please write your answer here:

30. Was the anonymized data suitable in quality and structure for training purposes?

Please write your answer here:

31. Did the platform provide an advanced search function for datasets?

Please write your answer here:

32. Were the search filters and parameters sufficient to narrow down relevant datasets?

Please write your answer here:

33. Was the search feature responsive and performant?

Please write your answer here:

34. Were the search results relevant and comprehensive?

Please write your answer here:

35. Could you easily link or bookmark datasets for further processing?

Please write your answer here:

36. Were you able to link anonymized datasets together for analysis?

Please write your answer here:

37. Did the platform provide automated or guided tools for data linkage?

Please write your answer here:

38. Was linkage accuracy consistent across datasets?

Please write your answer here:

39. Could you verify that re-identification was not possible post-linkage?

Please write your answer here:

40. Did the platform improve your ability to perform rich or multi-source analysis?

Please write your answer here:

41. Additional comments

Please write your answer here:

Section 4. SIESTA Platform Operator (admin)

For all questions in this group (except the last one), you can simply answer with "Yes" ("Y") or "No" ("N"). However, the short text field permits you also to elaborate on your answer. Please feel free to use it for any additional comments or explanations.

Some questions may not apply to you, or you may not be able to answer them at this time. Please feel free to skip any such questions. If you find that you cannot answer most of the survey, please use the final section to explain why.

1. Did you use the secure container service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

2. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '92 [D1]' (1. Did you use the secure container service?)

Please write your answer here:

3. Did the service distribute computing workloads in a way to optimize the performance?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D1.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

4. Do secure containers meet your security and compliance requirements?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D1.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

5. Did the quota system help prevent overutilization and ensure fair access?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D1.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

6. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D1.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

7. Did you use the secure storage service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D7.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

9. Did the performance of the secure storage meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D7.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

10. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D7.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

11. Did you use the secure virtual machine service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

12. Is the process of setting up a secure virtual machine user-friendly?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D11.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

13. Did the performance of the secure virtual machines meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D11.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

14. Did you find the secure virtual machine service reliable?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D11.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

15. Could you configure the network access to the secure virtual machine?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D11.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

16. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D11.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

17. Did you use the data sync & share service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

18. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D17.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

19. Did the performance of the service meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D17.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

20. Could file and directory permissions be adjusted as requested?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D17.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

21. Was the AAI integration seamless?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D17.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

22. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D17.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

23. Did you use the Data Lake service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

24. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D23.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

25. Did the performance of the service meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D23.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

26. Was it possible to manage granular access controls?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D23.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

27. Does the data lake provide all required functionalities?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D23.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

28. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D23.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

29. Did you use the bulk data transfer service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

30. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D29.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

31. Did the performance of the service meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D29.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

32. Were you able to transfer large file with this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D29.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

33. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D29.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

34. Did you use the interactive analytics service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

35. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D34.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

36. Did the performance of the service meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D34.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

37. Did you assess the security of the service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D34.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

38. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D34.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

39. Did you use the web application service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

40. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D39.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

41. Did the performance of the service meet your expectations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D39.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

42. Was the service providing the required applications?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D39.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

43. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D39.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

44. Did you use the image registry service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

45. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D44.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

46. Did this service reduce risks related to vulnerable code execution?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D44.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

47. Were images regularly checked for vulnerabilities?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D44.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

48. Are all required images available from your application?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D44.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

49. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D44.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

50. Did you use the code repository service

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

51. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D50.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

52. Could user and group permissions be correctly configured?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D50.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

53. Did you use the code repository service for managing technical documentation and user support?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D50.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

54. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D50.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

55. Did you use the monitoring and auditing service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

56. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D55.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

57. Did the service provide enough space for storing all required audit logs?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D55.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

58. Could access logs be used for audit reporting?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D55.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

59. Could you assess the quality of the audit logs?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D55.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

60. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D55.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

61. Did you use the authorisation and authentication service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

62. Was the service easy to use and sufficiently documented?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D61.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

63. Did the service provide all required functionalities?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D61.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

64. Were you able to connect to your identity provider?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D61.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

65. Were you able to manage users and groups in your use case?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D61.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

66. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D61.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

67. Did you use the dynamic DNS service?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

68. What improvements would you suggest for this service?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

D67.NAOK == "Y"

Please write your answer here:

69. Which certificate authority did you use for securing your services and data transfers?

Please write your answer here:

70. Concerning certificate authority, would you have any suggestions?

Please write your answer here:

71. Were you able to request assistance or to report security incidents to the SIESTA platform administrators?

Please write your answer here:

72. Are any services missing?

Please write your answer here:

73. Additional comments

Please write your answer here:

DRAFT DOCUMENT. STILL NOT APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION.

